

An approach to quantifying the key greenhouse gas emissions in California concrete production

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Objective

The objective of this study is to develop a cohesive, unified dataset of life cycle inventories - needed to quantify the effects of material, energy, waste, and emission flows on the environmental impacts of concrete. The models developed will consider GHG emissions, namely CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O emissions, for the key components of cement and concrete production in California. The structure of the data will allow for tailoring of inputs to capture variations in different regions around the world. This allows the user to adapt for production in other regions or for importing material from other regions.

1. Introduction

The nation's concrete transportation infrastructure is not being sufficiently modernized and augmented to meet growing demands from increases in population and economic activity. Current stock and new concrete infrastructure that are anticipated in the coming decades need to be transformed in fundamental ways to reduce environmental burdens. This work focuses on the formation of requisite datasets to support informed decision-making and management solutions for innovative concrete infrastructure that can meet performance requirements while mitigating environmental impacts.

Robust datasets are needed to accurately assess the environmental impacts and financial costs associated with alternative concrete mixtures, use-phases, and end-of-life options. Many cost implications from the construction industry are available through sources such as the RS Means [1], but data that reflect US-specific environmental impacts from concrete are limited to Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and individual academic studies (e.g., [2]). These current assessment methods lead to difficulties in drawing direct comparisons between material alternatives and consideration of adjustments in concrete design.

To build a foundation for advancement of work in this area, this study focuses on the development of a database that can readily be used by decision makers to compare GHG emissions of varying concrete mixtures.

2. Methods

For this work, both process-based (e.g., emissions from calcination) and energy-based emissions (e.g., emissions from combusting fossil fuels for thermal energy) were considered to assess GHG emissions. The process-based emissions were calculated from values reported that could be differentiated from energy-derived emissions. The energy-based emissions were determined through energy demands and energy-derived emissions (factors for energy modeling and sources are discussed below); emissions from fuels used in transportation were included as energy-based emissions. The GHGs that were considered in this work are CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O. These gases were assessed in terms of CO₂-eq using the 100a global warming potentials from the

IPCC [3]. The scope of the impacts assessed are outlined in Figure 1. Comparisons of concrete mixtures were based on a cubic meter of production. While the use phase was not directly a component of the environmental impact comparisons, it was considered through the inclusion of performance-based comparison methods in the accompanying sections of this project.

Figure 1. Scope Diagram (gray dashed lines are considered within the scope of assessment; emissions calculated based on process- and energy-based emissions, which included transportation emissions).

Specific modeling assumptions for individual concrete constituents, transportation, batching, and end-of-life are stipulated individually below:

Cement Production. The production of cement has the single most notable process-based GHG emissions of the materials assessed. These emissions are from the calcination reaction. These emissions were calculated based on a simple stoichiometric balance of $\text{CaCO}_3 + \text{energy} \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$ in the production of clinker. These emissions were then scaled assuming 65% lime content in clinker and 5% gypsum in cement. Energy demand for kilns was based on efficiencies by type from the Cement Sustainability Initiative [4], using energy demand values reported for the world average in the year 2016. The electricity requirements, by kiln type, were from a report prepared for the Portland Cement Association (PCA) [5].

Mineral Admixtures. Several different mineral admixtures were modeled for this work. These admixtures included both naturally occurring materials and byproducts from other systems. Of the naturally occurring materials, limestone filler, gypsum, natural pozzolans, and interground limestone were modeled. Additionally, calcined clays were considered, which are clays that require additional calcining to become desirable supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs). The energy demand for limestone filler was based on [6], with all energy demand adapted to reflect the California electricity grid using lower heating value (LHV) factors from [7]. The quarrying and crushing of gypsum and natural pozzolans were modeled as requiring the same energy as that for the limestone filler. Interground limestone, was modeled using the energy required for the limestone filler with an additional electricity demand for grinding with cement. The additional grinding electricity was approximated at the lower end of clinker electricity demand. Namely, it was modeled as 30% of the 110 kWh/t reported by [8], which is on the lower end of energy reported by [9]. Even though studies have shown that intergrinding, especially in a laboratory setting could lead to higher processing times to achieve the desired gradation, this lower end was selected because limestone is softer than clinker. For the production of calcined clay, thermal energy and electricity demands were based on existing models [10].

Fly ash, shale ash, blast furnace slag, silica fume, and rice hull ash were the byproduct admixtures considered in this work. Fly ash was modeled as not requiring any energy inputs, which is based on an assumption published by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) [11]. For this work, shale ash and silica fume were modeled as having the same impacts as fly ash. This assumption was based on the modeling presented by the PCA, which stated a similar collection method for silica fume would be used to fly ash, resulting in negligible environmental impacts [12]. Here, that premise is extended to shale ash as well. Rice hull ash, similar to the fly ash, was modeled as not requiring any energy for generation. However, it was assumed that a certain amount of grinding would be necessary to achieve the desired gradation, and the electricity for this grinding was based on [13]. The energy demand for the production of slag was based on an industry EPD [14].

Hemp for Hempcrete. While hemp fibers have been studied for use in concrete (e.g., [15]), hempcrete is a term most typically used to refer to a insulative brick solidified in a hydraulic binder [16]. In Hempcrete, the typical component of the hemp plant used is the woody core of the stalks, referred to as hurds or shives [17,18]. Here, hemp hurds are modeled based on an environmental impact model for the cultivation of hemp plants and extraction of their fibrous components [19]. The quantity of energy necessary to extract hurds from the hemp plant was

determined based on a mass allocation of the mass of hurd relative to the mass of other fibers that are extracted and used from this bast species (based on [20]). For hemp hurds, there will be an additional uptake of CO₂ during photosynthesis and water demand depending on agricultural conditions that are not presented in this work.

Aggregates. For fine and coarse aggregates, the energy demand required was based on a report from the PCA [12], with slightly lower energy demands being reported for fine aggregates than for coarse aggregates.

Chemical Admixtures. Six chemical admixtures were modeled in this work: (a) plasticizers and superplasticizers; (b) air entrainers; (c) hardening accelerators; (d) set accelerators; (e) water resisting admixtures; and (f) retarders. For each of these (a-f), energy demands were based on EPDs from the European Federation of Concrete Admixtures Associations Ltd.: [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], and [26], respectively.

Batching. The energy demand for batching was based on a report from the Lawrence Berkeley National Lab [27]. In this work, water was modeled as not requiring any energy to get to the site. While this is an underestimate in most cases, the variability in energy demand and associated emissions with getting the water to the concrete manufacturing site was considered too great to include and small relative to other emissions considered.

Transportation. Both energy demand and GHG emissions for three modes of transportation (truck, rail, and ship) are reported in this model. For transportation by truck, energy demand is based on the average value reported by [28]. For energy demand for the other modes and GHG emissions for all three modes, inputs were based on median from distributions fit to data from [29,30] (for these distributions, a single point was used if there was only one datum, a uniform distribution was used if there were two data points, a triangular distribution was used if there were three, and a lognormal distribution was used for four or more data points). However, rather than use the energy demand to assess greenhouse gas emissions, as is done for other processes, the GHG emissions from the modes of transportation are used directly.

Thermal Energy. For the thermal energy demands discussed above, GHG emissions were modeled for different fuel resources. These emissions factors were based on median results for GHG emissions from estimates and modeling assumptions discussed in [31]. For the kilns, the thermal energy fuel mix used was based on national statistics reported by the United States Geologic Survey (USGS) [32]. Additional thermal energy mixes can be added to the spreadsheet developed and used with the emissions factors provided to estimate GHG emissions with alternative energy resources.

Electricity. For the electricity demands discussed above, GHG emissions were modeled for different fuel resources. These emissions factors were based on median results for GHG emissions from estimates and modeling assumptions discussed in [31]. All processes requiring electricity were modeled as occurring in California, with the exception of the blast furnace slag. The California electricity mix was based on in-state generation from the California Energy Commission [33]. The blast furnace slag production was modeled as occurring in Pennsylvania, with the Pennsylvania electricity mix modeled based on USDOE data [34]. Additional electricity grids can be added to the spreadsheet and used with the emissions factors provided to estimate GHG emissions with alternative energy resources.

End of Life. To capture an approximation for end-of-life related GHG emissions, demolition and crushing energy demand was modeled based on data from [35].

To perform a simple assessment for concrete mixtures with varying concrete constituents, an intermediary step in which all flows for any given constituent or process that could be used in the mixtures (e.g., natural pozzolans, batching) was tabulated. These constituents and processes can then be used to determine GHG emissions from production of concrete by being weighted based on the mass of constituents used in a given concrete mixture.

These constituent and process impacts from the intermediary step are utilized in the spreadsheet in an example impact assessment of a mixture. Namely, to implement an example of the calculation of GHG emissions for a concrete mixture, a mixture with limestone filler is presented. Transportation for the constituents of this mixture are listed in Table 1. In this example, all transportation was modeled as being transported by truck.

Table 1. Transportation distances modeled for the example assessment of GHG emissions from the production of a concrete mixture

constituent	distance (km)
Portland Cement	20
Limestone, interground	20
Limestone Filler	150
Natural Pozzolans	150
Shale Ash	150
Calcined Clay	150
Silica Fume	150
Fly Ash	2000
Blast Furnace Slag	2000
Fine Aggregates	100
Coarse Aggregates	100
Superplasticizer	1000
Water	0

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